

doi 10.5281/zenodo.12651345

Vol. 07 Issue 05 May - 2024

Manuscript ID: #01437

The Effects of Feedback on the Professional Development of Student Teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon

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Abstract

This study investigated the effects of feedback during clinical supervision and its impact on the Professional Development of Student Teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. It is based on the problem of inadequate feedback during clinical supervision which has negative impacts on the professional development of student teachers. The general objective of the study was to find out the impact of clinical supervision on the professional development of student teachers. The specific objective was to investigate the impact of Feedback during clinical supervision on the professional development of student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. Based on this, research question was formed and hypothesis generated. The scope was limited to student – teachers and supervisors in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. The sample population was 346 student teachers and 08 supervisors. The study made use of the mixed method design and used the purposive sampling for selecting the schools and the class for the study. It also made use of the inferential and descriptive statistics. The instruments for data collection were the questionnaire for student – teachers, interview for the supervisors and cooperating teachers and observation guide. The questionnaires were made up of items about feedback during clinical supervision. The supervisors were equally interviewed on this. From the results we have the following conclusions: 81.1% of supervisors do not provide feedback during teaching practice with their supervisees. This means that there is a significant impact on feedback for supervision on the professional development of student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. The study recommends that supervision schools be opened to train supervisors. Also, those serious sanctions be given to supervisors who do not carry out clinical supervision appropriately during teaching practice.

Keywords:

Clinical supervision, feedback, teaching practice, professional development

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Introduction and Problem

Students' achievement is closely linked to teachers' input (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007). One way to ensure that teachers are providing effective instruction is to implement effective supervision. Regrettably, supervision has been equated to inspection, an administrative task that has to be achieved by an authority referred to as "inspector" whose job is to evaluate and control teachers' performance. (Sergiovanni & Starratt, 2007). Sergiovanni went on stressing that traditional supervision is carried out in a way that makes teachers feel they are subordinates whose performance has to be examined. Since clinical supervision seems to be part and parcel of the educational system, teachers should be trained so that they develop in their profession. To develop professionally, a teacher centred supervisory approach needs to be adopted by supervisors. Being bottom up, clinical supervision, as opposed to the traditional supervision, incites teachers in getting engaged in reflective teaching practices with the assistance of a supervisor who would adopt the role of a facilitator and communicator (Poole, 2012). Essentially, clinical supervision in education involves a teacher receiving information from a colleague who has observed the teacher's performance and who serves both as a mirror and a sounding board to enable the teacher to critically examine and possibly alter his or her professional practice. Giving and receiving feedback in clinical supervision cannot be overstated. Feedback is a valuable tool for improving clinical skills and enhancing patient care. It provides a platform for professional growth and development. Giving and receiving feedback in clinical supervision is essential as it promotes professional growth and improved patient care. But giving feedback constructively and effectively during supervision has shown to be challenging as it requires specific strategies to ensure it is well-received and valuable to the supervisee. The study therefore sets out to investigate the extent to which supervisors provide feedback during Clinical supervision and how this influences the teachers professional development in student teachers of higher technical teacher training colleges in Cameroon. It hypothesizes that there is no significant relationship between the impact of Feedback and the professional development of Student teachers in Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon.

Theory and Concept

In arguing for feedback in Clinical supervision, the study employs the theory of Cognitive Apprenticeship of Collins A, Brown S.J. & Newman, S.E. (1989). This involves the learning-through-guided-experience on cognitive and metacognitive, rather than physical, skills and processes. The goal of cognitive apprenticeship is to address the problem of inert knowledge and to make the thinking processes of a learning activity visible to both the students and the teacher. The teacher is then able to employ the methods of traditional apprenticeship (modeling, coaching, scaffolding, and fading) to effectively guide student learning (Collins, Brown & Newman, 1989).

According to Collins et al (1991), Cognitive apprenticeship supports the effective integration of academic and vocational education so students construct their own understanding of Learning in cognitive apprenticeship occurs through legitimate peripheral participation, a process in which newcomers enter on the periphery and gradually move toward full participation (Collins et al., 1991). Apprenticeship is closely associated with learning a skilled trade; the journeyman works with the apprentice and shows him how a task is completed. The journeyman offers words of encouragement or correction and practices with the apprentice until he is able to do it without assistance or supervision. Then, he too becomes proficient and is able to pass on his skills to others. This cycle defines apprenticeship as one learns how to do specific tasks by working and learning from another. The thinking process of apprenticeship is visible to all involved, which makes it an ideal method of learning. This model is supported by Vygotsky's theory of social constructivism (1978, 1987).

The cognitive apprenticeship approach, consists of six teaching methods: modelling, coaching, scaffolding, articulation, reflection, and exploration. The six methods, in turn, break down into three groups. The first group - modelling, coaching, and scaffolding- represents the core and is designed to help students acquire an integrated set of cognitive skills through observation and supported practice. The second group -articulation and reflection- is designed to focus students' observations of expert problem solving and to gain control of their own problem solving strategies and metacognitive skills. The final group -exploration- is intended to encourage learner autonomy, problem formulation by the self, and transfer. Roles of cognitive masters and students and the target outcomes for these six teaching methods.

In Modelling (and explaining), the cognitive master models process to show "how the process unfolds" or how the mentor/peer function in certain situations. In other words, an expert performs a task so that students can observe his actions and build a conceptual model of the processes required for task accomplishment. The provision of a conceptual model contributes significantly to success in teaching complex skills without resorting to lengthy practice of isolated sub skills. In cognitive domains, this necessitates the externalization of internal cognitive processes. Tacit processes are brought into the open so that students can observe, enact, and practice the requisite skills. Explaining involves giving "reasons why it happens that way" or providing rationale for processes. Learners see the process for problem-solving and see different ways to trouble-shoot. They also observe what is happening and why things happen the way they do.

In Coaching, the cognitive master provides assistance to learners as needed by providing individual attention on difficulties the learners are having, providing help at "critical times" or when the learners most need it, providing requested assistance as needed and withdrawing unneeded help, and asking relevant questions to stimulate thought and provide a different point-of-view of situations. Here students are engaged in problem-solving activities that require them to appropriately apply and actively integrate subskills and conceptual knowledge. In this way, conceptual and factual knowledge are exemplified and situated in their contexts of use, thereby grounding the knowledge in experience and making learning meaningful. Consequently, this approach helps to avoid learning outcomes where knowledge remains bound to surface features of problems as they appear in textbooks. The expert coaches students by providing hints, feedback, and reminders to assist students to perform closer to his level of accomplishment. As they coach, they sometimes offer additional modelling or explanation. In scaffolding (and fading), the cognitive master assists students to manage a more complex task performance. If necessary, the cognitive master completes those parts of the task that students have not yet mastered. This method may entail students engaging in legitimate peripheral participation (Lave & Wenger, 1991). That is, students participate in the practice of an expert, but only to the extent that they can handle and with the amount of responsibility that they are capable of assuming. Scaffolding is coupled with fading, the gradual removal of the cognitive master's support as students learn to manage more of the task on their own.

The interplay between observation, scaffolding, and increasingly independent practice aids students in developing the metacognitive skills of self-monitoring and self-correction and in achieving integrated skills and knowledge characteristic of expertise. Thus, modelling and coaching support students' efforts to "grow into" domain competence while scaffolding and fading support students' efforts to "grow out of" dependence on the expert.

In articulation, learners are required to "explain and think about what they are doing" by making their knowledge explicit. Therefore, they can see other applications for their knowledge, and test their

understanding of knowledge. The role of the cognitive master here is to encourage students to explicate their knowledge, reasoning, and problem-solving strategies. Such activities provide the impetus for students to engage in the refinement and reorganization of knowledge. Such tasks require students to participate in generating knowledge and evaluating the outcomes of knowledge building activities as part of collaborative learning activities.

Also, in reflection, learners reflect on work they have already performed and analyze or deconstruct it. Through this process, they can increase their “awareness of their own knowledge” (also called metacognition) and be able to compare what they know with what others know. Here, the cognitive master role is to provoke students to compare their problem-solving processes with the master's work, with that of other students, and with an internal cognitive model of the relevant expertise. Such comparisons aid students in diagnosing their difficulties and in incrementally adjusting their performance until they achieve competence. Reflection is facilitated by the provision of abstracted replay that contrasts students’ own performance with that of the expert (Collins & Brown, 1988). Shared articulation and reflection usually magnifies the benefits of these processes.

During exploration, learners try out different hypotheses, methods and strategies by exploring their project and work environment. Through exploration they can learn how to set achievable goals, form and test hypotheses, and make independent discoveries. Here, the cognitive master role is to encourage students to be independent learners; identify personal interests; and pursue personal goals. In fact, forcing students to engage in exploration teaches them how to frame interesting questions and to identify difficult problems on their own. Giving students an interesting assignment with only generally formulated goals gives students the latitude to explore and thus extend their understanding of a subject. Exploration can also help students gain confidence in their ability to learn on their own.

In relevance the learner or student – teacher, the supervisor and or cooperating teacher through collaborative dialogue, modelling, coaching and mentoring, guides the student teacher into acquiring teaching competencies to enhance professional development. The supervisor coaches the student-teacher by providing hints, feedback, and reminders to assist the student - teacher to perform closer to his level of accomplishment. As they coach, they sometimes offer additional modelling or explanation. In scaffolding, the supervisor or cooperating teacher guides the student - teacher to manage a more complex task performance. All this is done during teaching practice to enable the student – teacher acquire skills that will enhance his / her professional development.

Feedback during Clinical Supervision

Endeley (2014) states that a successful student teaching experience is the keystone of pre-service teacher preparation. To her, Clinical supervision is a means of ensuring that student teaching is carried out most effectively through systematic planning, observation, and feedback. The clinical supervision model is designed to help teachers grow professionally. It recognizes that each student teacher is different and no student teacher will be a carbon copy of "the ideal teacher" or teach every lesson exactly according to a given model. This is because people are different and have different ways of going about teaching.

Olivia and Pawlas (2004), had earlier indicated that the three stages of clinical supervision are Planning for supervision, Class observation and Feedback conference.

Feedback is a two-way respectful and mutually beneficial process between supervisors and teachers and student teachers. It occurs through communication (written or verbal) between the supervisor and

the teacher, before, during and after a supervisory or other learning event, and objectively provides the teacher with a clear understanding of the level of their competency at a particular time, helps them to adjust and grow professionally. It also enables the learner to express views about the learning experience which enables a supervisor to reflect on and improve their supervisory skills and performance (Health Workforce Australia, 2013). Feedback supports students to close the gap between current and required performance (Allen & Molloy, 2015; Burgess & Mellis 2015; Schartel 2012) to attain competence (Allen & Molloy, 2015). Delany & Molloy (2018) describe feedback as vital for teaching and correcting learners, revealing learners' blind spots, reinforcing learning, motivating learners, identifying gaps, improving patient care, and collaboration. Jorissen (2006) states;

“The post-observation conference I believe is one of the most important aspects of any clinical supervision”.

According to Jorissen (2006) , the post-observation conference (feedback) is an excellent catalyst for teachers' self-reflection and individual professional growth. However, for any post-observation conference to be successful, preparation is important, in two aspects; questioning and feedback.

Professional Development

Fullan (2006) state that professional development involves workshops, programs and related activities that are designed to enable teachers acquire new ideas, skills and competences necessary for improvement in the classroom. He further gave five points which represent a clarion call to radically change our concept to what teacher learning should entail; firstly, that professional development is a major obstacle to progress in teacher learning. Again, he supported Elmore's observation in that teachers need to learn to do the right thing in the setting where they work. Thirdly he stated that student learning pends on every teacher learning all the time. The fourth observation is that the first three components depend on deprivatizing teaching as teachers work together to continuously improve instruction. The last component is that teachers working conditions are inimical to the four previous points. professional development therefore is a combination of tools, strategies, resources and training sessions for educators (student teachers) to improve their teaching quality and effectiveness. These resources allow teachers to further their knowledge in their subject areas and allows for mentorship and the opportunity to learn new teaching techniques.

Methodology

This study was conducted in 4 Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges chosen from the South, Littoral, North West and South West Regions Cameroon. The main population of the study was made up of all the student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training colleges in Cameroon. The target population of the study was made up of all final year student-teachers and teachers of Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. The accessible population was made up of all student teachers from all the departments in the selected schools. 346 student teachers and 08 supervisors from all departments of all the HTTTCs Cameroon were purposively sampled for the study.

Research Design

The study adopted a mixed approach of both quantitative and qualitative methods research design which employed questionnaire, interview guides, and observation checklist for research instruments.

Analysis of quantitative data

The data collected from field were processed using EpiData 3.1 and the Pearson test was used to test the hypotheses.

Analysis of qualitative data

On the other, the qualitative data derived from open ended questions were analysed using the thematic analysis approach with the aid of themes, groundings/frequency and quotations. Finally, findings were presented using frequency distribution and thematic tables and on charts with all inferential statistics presented at 95% level of confidence interval with alpha set at 0.05 levels, accepting 5% margin of error.

Findings

Among the 344 student teachers successfully sampled, 30.3% (105) were from ENSET Douala, 27.3% (94) were from HTTTC Kumba, 21.8% (75) were from HTTTC de Ebolowa and 20.3% (70) were from ENSET Bambili. The objective of the study was

To investigate the impact of Feedback on the Professional Development of Student Teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon

Table 1

Student Teachers Opinion on Feedback

Statements	Stretched				Collapsed		Mean	Std. Dev
	SA	A	D	SD	SA/A	D/SD		
Your supervisor has a post conference with you.	4 (1.2%)	59 (17.2%)	149 (43.4%)	131 (38.2%)	63 (18.4%)	280 (81.6%)	1.81	.753
If yes, is it successful?	5 (1.5%)	55 (16.0%)	142 (41.4%)	141 (41.1%)	60 (17.5%)	283 (82.5%)	1.78	.763
He has a post conference with you always.	2 (0.6%)	50 (14.6%)	144 (42.0%)	147 (42.9%)	52 (15.2%)	291 (84.8%)	1.73	.725
He rarely has a post conference with you.	132 (38.5%)	152 (44.3%)	55 (16.0%)	4 (1.2%)	284 (82.8%)	59 (17.2%)	1.80	.744
He/she asks about the challenges you had while teaching.	6 (1.7%)	59 (17.2%)	132 (38.4%)	146 (42.4%)	65 (19.0%)	278 (81.0%)	1.78	.788
Your supervisor discusses the strengths and weaknesses of your lesson with you.	9 (2.6%)	62 (18.1%)	123 (35.9%)	149 (43.4%)	71 (20.7%)	272 (79.3%)	1.80	.826

He/she gives you guidance on how to make it better next time.	10 (2.9%)	62 (18.1%)	122 (35.6%)	149 (43.4%)	72 (21.0%)	271 (79.0%)	1.80	.834
He/she encourages you to do better.	9 (2.6%)	60 (17.5%)	133 (38.8%)	141 (41.1%)	69 (20.1%)	274 (79.9%)	1.82	.812
Your supervisor asks you about your next lesson and how you intend to go about it.	9 (2.6%)	63 (18.4%)	121 (35.4%)	149 (43.6%)	72 (21.1%)	270 (78.9%)	1.80	.829
I am comfortable with the way being supervised.	10 (2.9%)	64 (18.7%)	124 (36.3%)	144 (42.1%)	74 (21.6%)	268 (78.4%)	1.82	.835
Multiple Responses Set (MRS)	58 (1.9%)	525 (17.0%)	1218 (39.5%)	1285 (41.6%)	583 (18.9%)	2503 (81.1%)	1.79	.791

* Item with coding reversed during calculation of MRS: **Item excluded from calculation of MRS

Figure 1

Student Teachers Opinion on Feedback

In all, based on feedback, only 18.9% of student teachers with a mean of 1.79 below the cutoff point of 2.5 agreed that their supervisors related with them while a majority 81.1% disagreed. Specifically, while 18.4% (63) of student teachers agreed to have a post conference with their supervisors, majority them 81.6% (280) disagreed. Similarly, only 15.2% (52) of student teachers agreed to always have post-conference with supervisors while many 84.8% (291) disagreed. Furthermore, only 17.5% (60) of student teachers agreed to have successful feedback with supervisor while majority of them 82.5%

(283) disagreed. Furthermore, only 19.0% (278) of student teachers agreed that their supervisors asked about challenges faced when teaching whereas majority of them 81.0% (278) denied.

Also, 21.0% (72) of student teachers were informed of the strengths and weaknesses of their lesson notes by their supervisors while 79.0% (271) did not not. Also, 20.7% (71) of student teachers agreed to be given guidance on how to make better their lessons next time while 79.3% (272) disagreed. Similarly, only 20.1% (69) of student teachers were encouraged to do better by supervisors while majority 79.9% (274) disagreed. Similarly, only 21.1% (72) of student teachers agreed that their supervisors asked about their next lesson and how they intended to go about it while majority 78.9% (270) disagreed. Finally, only 21.6% (74) of student teachers were comfortable with the way they were being supervised while majority 78.4% (268) were not comfortable.

Table 2

Observation by Researcher on Feedback

Items	Very often	Often	Not very often	Never	Mean	Std. Deviation
Have a post conference after observing the supervisee	0	0	8	20	1.29	.460
Explains the strengths and weaknesses of the lesson to supervisee	0	0	7	21	1.25	.441
Guides and directs supervisee on the way forward.	0	0	7	21	1.25	.441
Listens to the concerns of the supervisee.	0	0	4	24	1.14	.356
Works together with supervisee on subsequent lessons.	0	1	3	24	1.18	.476
Asks about next lesson	0	1	5	22	1.25	.518
There is mutual dialogue and not a shouting session.	0	1	4	23	1.21	.499

No of observations 28

In line with student teachers opinion, observation carried out by the researcher showed that supervisors did not give feedback to student teachers as indicated with a low mean values ranging from 1.21 to 1.29, below the cutoff point of 2.5. To be explicit, observation carried out by the researcher showed that many supervisors did not often have a post conference after observing the supervisee, explains the strengths and weaknesses of the lesson to supervisee, guide and direct supervisees on the way forward, listen to the concerns of the supervisees, work together with supervisees on subsequent lessons and ask about next lesson.

Table 3***Supervisors Opinion on Issues Related to Feedback of Supervisees during Teaching Practice***

Questions	Themes	Quotations
After every lesson, do you meet with your supervisees and discuss on the strength and weaknesses of their lesson?	Yes	“Yes, I do discuss the strength and weakness with the students”.
		“I do inform the students of the weaknesses and strength”
		“Yes, I do”.
		“I do”.
Do you give advice on how to improve on subsequent lessons?	Not frequent	“Not all the time”
		“I sometimes made the students know of their strength and weaknesses”
		“Not always”
	Yes	“I give them advice”
Do you think your presence and feedback has a role to play in making student – teachers develop teaching skills and grow professionally?		“Yes, I advise them”.
		“Yes”
		“I advise the students were lacking on the need to improve on next lessons”.
		“Yes, especially when I realise that the student is lacking”.
	Yes	“Definitely”.
		“Of course, it do have a role in the professional growth”
		“Yes, it has a role play in their professional development”.
		“Of course”.
		“Definitely, my presence matters a lot in helping the students develop in their teaching skills and grow professionally”.
		“Yes, sure”

Based on supervisors’ opinion in relation to feedback, some of them said after every lesson, they met with their supervisees and discussed on the strengths and weaknesses of their lesson as depicted in the statements “*Yes, I do discuss the strengths and weaknesses with the students*”, “*I do inform the students of the weaknesses and strength.*” However, some of the supervisors did not meet frequently with their supervisees to discuss on the strengths and weaknesses of their lesson as depicted in the

statements “*Not all the time*”, “*I sometimes make the students know of their strengths and weaknesses*”

Furthermore, all eight supervisors interviewed said that they gave advice to their supervisees on how to improve on subsequent lessons as depicted in some of their statements “*I advise the students where lacking on the need to improve on next lessons*”, “*Yes, especially when I realise that the student is lacking*”.

Finally, all eight supervisors opine that their presence and feedback has a role to play in making student – teachers develop teaching skills and grow professionally as depicted in their statements “*Yes, it has a role play in their professional development*”, “*Of course*”, “*Definitely, my presence matters a lot in helping the students develop in their teaching skills and grow professionally*”. The supervisors’ opinion on feedback contradicted those of the student teachers and observations carried out by the researcher.

Verification of Hypothesis

Ho: there is no significant relationship between the impact of Feedback and the professional development of Student teachers in Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon

Score of the independent variable (feedback) was aggregated from 10 items and that for dependent variable (professional development of student teachers) was computed from 10 items. Result is presented on the table below.

Table 4

Relationship between Feedback and Professional Development of Student Teachers

Pearson test		Feedback	Professional Development of student teachers	Explanatory power of relationship in terms of % (Nagelkerke)
Planning	R-value	1	.649**	.772 (77.2%)
	p-value		.000	
	N	344	341	
Professional Development	R-value	.649**	1	
	p-value	.000		
	N	341	341	

***. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).*

At 0.05 cl and df=339, r-critical value is 0.105

Statistics showed that the calculated r-value is 0.649** five times higher than the critical value of 0.105 at df of 349. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was rejected and alternative retained. In other words, feedback has a significant, positive and strong impact on professional development of student teachers. The positivity of the correlation value implies that professional development of student teachers is more likely to increase when supervisors adequately provide feedback to student teachers

after supervision of instruction and this strong impact on professional development of student teachers was also support with a high explanatory power of 77.2%.

4) Discussion and Conclusion

Descriptively, only 18.9% of student teachers with a mean of 1.79 below the cutoff point of 2.5 agreed that supervisor relate to them while a majority 81.1% disagreed. In line with student teachers opinion, observation carried out by the researcher also showed that many supervisors do not give feedback to student teachers as indicated with a low mean values ranging from 1.21 to 1.29, below the cutoff point of 2.5 but, the supervisors on their own part said they provide feedback to students. And, further analysis showed that feedback has a significant, positive and strong impact on professional development of student teachers (R-value 0.649**, p -value =0.000). The positivity of the correlation value implies that professional development of student teachers is more likely to increase when supervisors adequately provide feedback to student teachers after supervision of instruction and this strong impact on professional development of student teachers is also support with a high explanatory power of 77.2%.

According to Delany & Molloy (2018):

Feedback is vital for teaching and correcting learners, revealing learners' blind spots, reinforcing learning, motivating learners, identifying gaps, improving patient care, and collaboration The post-observation conference I believe is one of the most important aspects of any clinical supervision. The post-observation conference is an excellent catalyst for teachers' self-reflection and individual professional growth. However, for any post-observation conference to be successful, preparation is important, in two aspects; questioning and feedback. (p.307)

This corroborates what Feeney (2007) found out. He said:

"Feedback should have a positive impact on teacher growth and student learning." He went on to say that there should be collaboration between administrators to establish professional goals that address student-learning outcomes. What this does is presents to teachers a clear focus with specific goals together with the necessary support. However, for effective feedback supervision needs to be connected to a framework/rubric. Moreover, teachers need to be able to read and comprehend the recommendations that are provided. In addition, administrators need to be well trained to provide teachers with effective feedback that will enhance teaching and learning in the classroom. Strategies should be suggested and time should be allowed for implementation. The teachers should, "collect and analyze student work to assess whether the strategy was effective in helping students meet the learning objective (p .194).

Despite its importance, feedback is inherently an emotive conversation for both the supervisor and student, which can be seen to threaten relationships, and therefore difficult to effectively engage in (Delany & Molloy, 2018).

The results ties with the Social – constructivist theory of Cognitive Apprenticeship of Hulum et al., (1989). They maintained that collaborative dialogue, modelling, coaching and mentoring guides the student teacher in to acquiring teaching competences that enhance their professional development.

The study corroborates that Provision of feedback is an integral part of the supervisory process. Feedback is a general term and to understand it fully, some questions that need to be answered

include: What constitutes “effective” feedback and what type of feedback is counterproductive to the supervisory relationship? When should one provide feedback? How much feedback is enough? This shows that it has an impact on the professional development of teachers.

Similarly, O'Reilly & Anderson (1980) noticed that when feedback was accurate, relevant, frequent, and helpful in advancing job skills, job satisfaction was higher. The level of trust in the supervisor played an important role in the receiver's willingness to accept feedback. The data suggested that the high trust subgroup perceived feedback to be more relevant, accurate and more significant in quantity than the low trust subgroup. Analysis further indicated that for feedback to have a positive impact, the receiver had to accurately perceive and respond to the message. Accurate perception of the message was questionable in cases where trust between supervisor and supervisee was low. Relevant and accurate feedback was especially important for the low trust subgroups. In conclusion, accuracy, relevance, frequency of feedback, as well as trust in the supervisor were key elements necessary for building a successful supervisory relationship (O'Reilly & Anderson, 1980).

This means that for students to successfully achieve their learning objectives, they require informative feedback that is timely and descriptive. Clinical supervisors, working with student teachers are best equipped to provide this timely feedback for continued reflection and growth. Supporting supervisors to deliver feedback that is meaningful enables student teachers to practice and progress through their learning. Hence, if feedback is absent, the professional development of student teachers will not be guaranteed.

Conclusively, it is evident that most supervisors do not give feedback to their supervisees during teaching practice. This has a negative impact on the professional development of student teachers in Higher Technical Teacher Training Colleges in Cameroon. The government should open more supervision schools where supervisors will be properly trained on how to go about supervision so that they can effectively carry out their tasks and help student teachers grow professionally. Furthermore, constant follow up should be done to ensure that supervisors are actually doing their jobs and the necessary sanctions given to defaulters.

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